
Deliverable D-JIP2-1.1: Kick-off meeting Workpackage 1

Responsible Partner: RIVM

Contributing partners: WBVR, Bfr, APHA,
IZS-AM, SVA

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GENERAL INFORMATION

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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Deliverable	D-JIP2-1.1 Kick –off meeting
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Leader	Kitty Maassen
Other contributors	RIVM, WBVR, Bfr, APHA, IZS-AM, SVA
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KICK OFF MEETING 28 & 29 MARCH 2018

AMSTERDAM, THE NETHERLANDS

Meeting Minutes

Goals:

- To get to know each other
- To discuss approach and concretise practical terms

Please notes that these minutes are not intended to provide a complete and detailed view of the kick off meeting. For more information see the slides of all presentations. For further information or questions please contact Kitty Maassen (cohesive@rivm.nl) or the work package leaders concerned.

Program:

March 28

11.30-12.30 Welcome & lunch

Plenary session:

12.35-12.55 Introductory round

It is agreed that email-addresses will be shared within the group

12.55-14.00 General introduction (Kitty Maassen) [presentation no. 1]

- EJP One Health, WP4 JIP

Kitty Maassen gives insight in the history of the development of the One Health EJP. Cohesive is part of WP 4 within the EJP; communication of surveillance data. There are two integrative programs within WP 4 of EJP: Cohesive & ORION. ORION is about interpretation of surveillance data, so ORION and COHESIVE are closely related.

A general EJP One Health website will be generated (not working yet), within there will be a part for the project Cohesive, behind a login. This will contain newsletters, press releases, short articles etcetera.

Considering reporting: there will be a year report each January, progress reports (September, December) and a final report at the end of Cohesive.

Finances are reported per institute.

If any questions arise, please contact Kitty.

- COHESIVE

One Health Structure in Europe

Background, objectives; improve collaboration between countries, like data sharing.

WP 1: Coordination, communication and sustainability -> Kitty Maassen (RIVM), deputy Hendrik-Jan Roest (WBVR)

WP2: Integrated risk-analysis at national level -> Kitty Maassen (RIVM), deputy Charlotte Cook (APHA)

WP3: Towards an EU One Health structure -> Elina Lahti (SVA), deputy Charlotte Cook (APHA)

WP4: Data platform to facilitate risk-analysis and outbreak control -> Armando Giovannini (IZS-AM), deputy Armin Weiser (BfR)

State of affairs WP1 [presentation no. 2]

Connect to other activities

- ORION and NOVA are invited to the kick-off meeting
- Join their kick-off meetings -> ORION April 18-20
- Join the cogwheel meeting of COMPARE -> April 12
- Interact with COST action NEOH -> guidelines for evaluation of OH initiatives
- Connect to EFSA, ECDC, EU -> EU and EFSA are present, there is contact with ECDC.

Workshops of Cohesive will be open for external partners, also for other (European?) countries.

Data Management Plan (Ann Lindberg) [presentation no. 3]

Integrative Support Function, short term integrative missions (exchange program; share knowledge. Guidelines are developed, probably ready in summer), Integrative mentoring (communication at management level).

Horizon 2020 rules; set up a data management plan (month 6; living document). Money is available for open access within the project funding.

The data must be FAIR:

Findable

Accessible

Interoperable

Re-usable

14.00-14.30 Introduction to work package 2; Kitty Maassen [presentation no. 4]

Goal: Provide common procedures and tools that can be used to improve human-veterinary collaboration in the area of (emerging) zoonoses.

Possibly even implement sustainable integrated One Health structure

At national level

Improve human-veterinary collaboration at national level, perhaps even built a sustainable structure

Introduction to work package 3; Elina Lahti [presentation no. 5]

Current ways of exchanging signals between countries and cross disciplines – pathway analysis

Select tools for Horizon scanning and signal detection

Retrospective systems analysis of detection of outbreaks

14.30-15.00 Coffee & tea break

15.00- 15.35 Introduction to work package 4, Armando Giovannini [presentation no. 6],

Introduction to task 4.1; Césaire Camma [presentation no. 7], Introduction to task 4.2; Armin Weiser [presentation no. 8] and Introduction to task 4.3 Thomas Selhorst [presentation no. 9]

15.35-16.15 Presentation partner projects/organisations:

- Presentation EJP ORION (Jörn Gethmann) [presentation no. 10]

One health surveillance initiative on harmonization of data collection and interpretation. The kick off meeting of ORION is next April. Representatives of COHESIVE will go to the kick off. Not all surveillance systems are known, so good to share what is already done, national and international (such as cost action Food borne parasites, an EU broad network)

- Presentation NOVA (Valerie De Waele) [presentation no. 11]

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost effective surveillance across the food chain. This is a research project.

- Presentation EFSA (Stef Bronzwaer) [presentation no. 12]
 - Zoonoses data collection

- WGS and other activities in area of zoonotic bacteria/foodborne agents

Public health data via ECDC are put in the joint database. EFSA puts in data from veterinary and foodborne pathogens.

Joint EFSA-ECDC annual EU summary report (EUSR) on zoonoses and food-borne outbreaks.

Other activities:

- VectorNet EFSA & ECDC collecting data on vectors and vector borne pathogens, related to animal and human health
- Sigma project; animal disease data collection-harmonisation / RA / risk factor analysis [see jpeg SIGMA information]
- Hep E conference
- Avian Influenza reports; collaboration between ECDC and EFSA
- Monitoring BSE, CWD, scrapie
- Joint ECDC-EFSA FBO assessment (ECDC-EFSA-SANTE C3-G4)
- EU RAA-Delphi study
- Presentation ECDC (Kitty Maassen represents ECDC, no representative of ECDC was able to join this meeting) [presentation no. 13]

Early Warning and response system (EWRS); rapid risk assessments

Epidemic intelligence; Threat Tracking Tool (TTT) & EPIS (communication platform, restricted to human experts, sometimes food safety authorities)

Development of a new system:

- All infectious diseases
- Access to all member states
- Zoonotic; also access for animal health experts, food safety authorities
- Collect epidemiological intelligence information
- High level requirements -> input from COHESIVE feasible (WP 3). This will start in Summer

Work sessions:

16.30-18.00 Discuss and concretise practical terms *within* work packages

- Overall goals and approach
- Focus on first year activities
- Contributors (who is doing what?)
- Meeting/teleconferences arrangements

WP 2

- 2.1 Guidelines national health structures
- 2.2 Structured decision making

WP 3

- 3.1 Explore current ways for exchange of signals
- 3.2 Select tools for horizon scanning
- 3.3 Retrospective system analysis of outbreak detection

WP 4

- 4.1 Molecular typing data and metadata
- 4.2 Development of a platform independent tracing framework
- 4.3 Development of a platform-independent risk modelling framework

[Coffee & tea available during sessions]

19.00 Dinner at restaurant Weesper

March 29

8.30-9.00 Walk in

Work sessions:

9.00-9.45 Extra time/finalizing: Discuss and concretise practical terms *within* work packages

9.45-11.30 Discuss approach and concretise practical terms *between* work packages, tasks, other projects and organisations in short parallel sessions.

- Identify joint activities in tasks
- Harmonization between WPs

Each below mentioned task/project/organisation will have a meeting point. Join the discussion you are interested in to talk about collaborative interactions. One *dedicated person will lead the discussion*. The sessions are approximately 20 minutes each. The last slot is open to give the opportunity to discuss combinations not yet covered or to further refine suggestions made in previous sessions.

Session 1:

- task 2.1 *Kitty Maassen*

- task 3.2 *Elina Lahti*

- task 4.1 *Cesare Camma*

During the session, two main issues were discussed: the use of standards for producing and analysing WGS data, and the possibility to explore databases and systems already existing in Europe.

Concerning the WGS standards, collaboration with COMPARE project (WP2, WP4 and WP7) as well as with ORION project (WP2) will be essential.

Moreover, it will be very interesting to explore the databases for Hepatitis A and E developed by RIVM and adopted by ECDC.

- ORION *Jörn Gethmann*

The detailed work plans of Cohesive and ORION are still under discussion, but, based on the proposals and as a result of the discussion, we identified an overlap in the following WP's:

- 1) Cohesive WP2: Within WP2 the partners deal with inventories and they will need clear definitions of surveillance terms. Within EJP ORION WP2 some similar aims are part of the Work Package.
- 2) In Cohesive WP4, there is a need for harmonization of metadata (WP 4.1) and NGS methods (analysis, epidemiological data, species, and matrix). There is an overlap to Orion WP WP2, WP 3 and WP1. The overlap will include ontologies and definitions and NGS.

As the kick-off meeting of ORION will be in Berlin from April 18-20, it will be necessary that members of the COHESIVE meeting will join ORION in order to define the overlap more in detail (Kitty and other members will join the meeting).

One important aspect is that the timelines between the partners need to be harmonized, too. E.g. for COHESIVE WP 4.1 and 4.2 the delivery of the NGS definitions and description is in month 17.

Based on the discussion at the ORION meeting the next steps will be planned.

Proposed to have a Skype conference between the partners in the relevant WP's in ORION and COHESIVE in May.

It will be discussed and agreed at the ORION meeting, too

Session 2:

- task 2.2 *Robin Simons*

Task 2.2 aims to develop a tool to aid in determining the appropriate type of risk assessment to carry out for a given situation (e.g. qualitative or quantitative) and provide an inventory of relevant risk assessment frameworks and tools that could be of use. In the discussion session two such tools were mentioned: a rapid risk assessment that has been developed by RIVM and the rRisk package for R developed by BfR. The burden of disease tool developed by ECDC was also suggested and that WHO may have recently updated their risk assessment guidelines. The rRisk tool will be further developed in WP 4.3 of COHESIVE. It was highlighted that the first stage of T2.2 is to identify appropriate contact points in each country from which to get information about the tools that they use. A questionnaire will then be sent, although in some cases an interview style approach may elicit better information. The structure/dissemination of the tool was discussed. Depending on the expertise available this may be a simple Excel based structure or potentially a web based tool. Discussion was had about whether it would be an appropriate fit into the platform independent risk modelling framework being developed in WP4.3.

- task 3.1 (and task 3.3) *Elina Lahti*

Retrospective systems analysis of outbreaks, Explore current ways of exchanging signals across borders – points of synergy

- Task 3.3 will investigate within country outbreaks up to the point of detection, although there may be points before this where potential signals are discussed across borders. This is likely to be informal.
- Not all participants will want to investigate outbreaks that involve more than one EU state, we may be able to introduce levels of investigation for each participant in 3.3 where only the 'deeper' or long time-series cases will cross in to task 3.3. Stepwise deliverables will enable partners to progress the analysis to a point that is relevant to the individual partner while maintaining a comparable analysis. Points of strength for detecting signals, or making decisions on investigations/controls will be relevant to task 3.1 as potential areas to focus on.
- There are existing systems for tracing animals and animal products across borders in Europe but we may not be able to track individuals to a high resolution outside country's 'own' data. We may be able to work with 3.1 to set up a protocol for 'matching' specific items to a high resolution. Possibly a small network of movements of a specific product/animal.

- task 4.2 *Armin Weiser*

In the session for task 4.2 there was a discussion about existing and potentially interesting data and model providers, especially for data on animal health and animal movement. National information on data structures may be available from NL, AT, IT, DE - contact points could be defined.

Additionally, there seems to be promising link to NOVA WP2 on purchase data with potentially additional information providers from NL and IT.

Promising discussions about modeling tracing within the MED-side was started and will be continued.

- NOVA *Charlotte Cook*

Novel approaches for design and evaluation of cost-effective surveillance across the food chain, ORION, COHESIVE – points of synergy

- Information gathering activities – mapping routes and detailing surveillance systems.

Many of the projects within the EJP are commencing with gathering information on the current state of One Health (OH) surveillance systems within each country, or targeted at a specific pathogen, this also includes the ORION project where a number of codex/inventories are planned. Part of the retrospective analysis will involve mapping out information flow systems, parts of this may be useful to the NOVA mapping/inventory task.

- Pathogen selection - The NOVA project is aimed at the food borne group of pathogens so will harmonise with some of the COHESIVE activities, although we have highlighted in workpackage discussions that foodborne pathogens have a well-structured, formal, notification route so would

perhaps focus on the 'difficult' pathogens within COHESIVE. Within the ORION project some of the groups are focusing on Salmonella as an example pathogen which would harmonise with NOVA.

Immediate points of harmonisation that could be investigated are: Joint workshops, oversight person/group for questionnaires (to avoid duplication), sharing results of questionnaires/workshops where information might be relevant to other projects. It will be necessary to have ongoing collaboration to avoid problems of deliverable deadlines clashing!

Session 3:

- EFSA/ECDC Stef Bronzwaer

Data interoperability is critical issue, so that different datasets can communicate to each other. Principle of the EJP projects is Open-Access. The EJP Data Management Plan recommends using Zenodo to share results and data sets. EFSA suggested to consider Knowledge Junction, which is food safety community, used by EFSA and national food authorities, established on Zenodo platform to share reports, datasets, images, videos, laboratory outputs, software, tools, models, code, protocols, study quality appraisal schemes, FAQs.: <https://zenodo.org/communities/efsa-kj?page=1&size=20>

- Identify WIN-WIN: Cohesive has significant resources (that are accessible in short timelines) and can help to build capacity, exchange best practices, address research questions, work in less formal framework. EFSA has long experience, enormous network and works in well-established legal framework. EJP/Cohesive could help to address knowledge gaps that are identified by EFSA (in scientific opinions).
- Avoid duplication and provide added value. It would be helpful if Cohesive describes in more detail what they will be doing and in particular what the aims/objectives are of each workpackage. Once described in more detail this should be consulted with other EJP projects, EFSA/ECDC and other parties.
- EJP has funds for PhD research. Consider PhD exchange among different MS authorities / EFSA / ECDC and consider other forms of staff exchange across EFSA/ECDC and Cohesive/EJP partners.
- Early informal exchange on signals (WP3): this will be a sensitive activity. Cohesive to define in more detail what objectives and methods aim to be, and discuss with EFSA/ECDC/EC.
- EFSA invited Cohesive to consider organising a future meeting in Parma.
- EFSA shared poster with information on SIGMA [see jpeg SIGMA image], and terminology list (glossary: <https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/glossary-taxonomy-terms>) developed by EFSA.
- Close communication will be critical and it may be good to establish EFSA / ECDC contact persons for the different work packages / projects.

- task 3.3 (see task 3.1) *Charlotte Cook*

- task 4.3 *Thomas Selhorst*

The R package rrisk will be set up as a Web application. It is modular and parts can be used separately from the main module (see rrisk distributions <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/rriskDistributions/rriskDistributions.pdf> ; prevalence estimation under misclassification BayesPEM access via Matthias Greiner). Link to BayesPEM: <http://shiny.bfr.bund.de/apps/bayespem/>

The tool will focus on the documentation and validation of risk assessments.

Please send us specific risk questions that you would like to be answered with a tool like this.

- Compare *Robin Simons*

Session 4: Open slots

NOVA/ORION: It is also important to make arrangements (data management plan) about the use of data of other projects within EJP, not just within Cohesive. Is that part of the consortium agreement?

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[10.30-10.45 Coffee & tea break]

Plenary session:

12.00-12.50 Sum-up of each WP (by WP leaders)

Share the yield of the different sessions with the WPs and in the sessions on collaboration. There is also opportunity to bring up bottlenecks, what has not been addressed (properly), suggestions, etc...

Wrap up WP2 [presentation no. 14]

Workshops together with WP2, 3 and 4

October

Wrap up WP3 [presentation no. 15]

Wrap up WP4 [presentation no. 16, 17, 18, 19]

12.50- Lunch and goodbye